

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT OF SOME DRUGS. PART III

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The dielectric constant of 8-hydroxyquinoline in pure molten state, as well as in solutions, and of 4 different 5:7-chloro-iodo substituted 8 hydroxyquinoline derivatives in benzene solution has been determined and the dipole moments calculated by applying the new equation. The compound 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline, which is reported to be most toxic, has highest dipole moment, 6.36D.

A number of chlorine- and iodine-substituted derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline have been reported to be very useful as internal antiseptics for amoebic infection (cf. Leake, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1944, 98, 196). The activity of these drugs is believed to be due to the liberation of iodine in the intestine. In order to find out the relation, if any, between the activity and dipole moment, the author has investigated the dipole moment of four isomeric chloro-iodo-8-hydroxyquinolines which were kindly supplied by Dr. T. N. Ghosh of the Bengal Immunity Research Laboratory, Calcutta. The dielectric constant of 8-hydroxyquinoline in pure molten state as well as in benzene and carbon tetrachloride solution has been determined for the first time and the dipole moments are calculated by applying the new equation of Jatkar *et al.* (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II). The results are presented in the following tables.

TABLE I

				 OH N			
		I. 8-Hydroxyquinoline.				$P_2 = 168.5$	
Temp.	ϵ	d	P			$\mu \times 10^{18}$	
1. Molten liquid :							
120°	8.052	1.135	901.6			2.28	
100°	8.287	1.150	941.6			2.28	
22°	3.126	—	—			—	
f_2	ϵ	d	P_2			$\mu \times 10^{18}$	
2. Solvent = benzene. Temp. = 25°.							
0.1029	2.8669	0.8987	1081.4			2.21	2.52
0.1315	3.0543	0.9073	1098.6			2.23	
Solvent = benzene. Temp. = 40°.							
0.1029	2.8282	0.8843	1067.4			2.25	
0.1315	2.9832	0.8931	1050.5			2.23	
3. Solvent = CCl ₄ . Temp. = 25°.							
0.0318	2.5453	1.5492	1076			2.21	
0.0371	2.6129	1.5606	1130			2.27	
0.0485	2.7372	1.5581	1132			2.27	
Solvent = CCl ₄ . Temp. = 40°.							
0.0371	2.4959	1.5423	981			2.20	
0.0485	2.7139	1.5373	1132			2.31	

TABLE II

f_{ν}	Temp	e	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$	μ_D
0.002534	18.5°	2.3074	0.8839	1147.5	2.14	2.4
"	48°	2.2513	0.8565	983.3	2.03	
III. 5-Iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline. $P_2 = 271.9$						
0.001120	19.5°	2.3023	0.8806	2014.4	3.11	
"	45°	2.2669	0.8565	1898.5	3.35	3.4
IV. 5:7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline. $P_2 = 236.3$						
0.001484	22°	2.3288	0.8763	3465.3	4.16	
"	40°	2.3063	0.8606	3548.5	4.31	5.9
V. 5:7-Di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline. $P_2 = 300.4$						
0.000519	20°	2.3232	0.8787	7989.7	6.36	
"	46°	2.2838	0.8549	7354.4	6.36	7.5

TABLE III

Table of moments.

Substance.	Solvent.	Temp.	$\mu \times 10^{18}$	μ_D
1. 8-Hydroxyquinoline (8 H Q.)	Pure liquid	100°-120°	2.28	
"	C_6H_6	25°-40°	2.23	2.52
"	CCl_4	25°, 40°	2.23	
2. 7-Chloro-7-iodo-8H.Q.	C_6H_6	18.5°, 40°	2.10	2.4
3. 5-Iodo-7-chloro-	"	19.5°, 40°	3.23	3.4
4. 5:7-Dichloro-	"	22°, 40°	4.23	5.9
5. 5:7-Di-iodo-	"	20°, 46°	6.36	7.5

DISCUSSION

In the 5:7-substituted 8-hydroxyquinolines, the 5-chloro-7-iodo- compound, which is known as 'Vioform' has the lowest moment (2.1), the moment of 5-iodo-7-chloro being 3.2D and that of 5:7-dichloro-(4:2-) and 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline having the highest (6.36) moment. Some chemical tests indicate that the iodine atom in 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline ($\mu = 3.26$) is more strongly bound than that in vioform *i.e.*, 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline ($\mu = 2.1$) (Ghosh *et al*, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1944, 21, 352) and as such the former compound is expected to liberate iodine more slowly than vioform in the system and thus may exert a more sustained therapeutic activity in the treatment of amoebiasis. However, no pharmacological data have been reported as yet.

5:7-Di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline is reported to be most toxic of these series of compounds, which has also the highest dipole moment. The 5:7-dichloro compound has not been investigated for its pharmacological properties. The moments calculated by applying Debyes' equation (μ_D) are systematically higher than the new values.

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